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OPTION OF MATHEMATICS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE

**EXPLORING DIGITAL LITERACY SKILLS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL
STUDENTS.**

CASE STUDY ESP RULI. RULI SECTOR GAKENKE DISTRICT

**A RESEARCH PROJECT REPORT SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT
FOR THE AWARD OF BACHELOR OF EDUCATION WITH HONOURS IN
MATHEMATICS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE**

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February 2026

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DEDICATION

We dedicate this work to: our beloved God, brothers, sisters, all our families and friends, our fellow students, as well as our supervisor and teachers for their contribution in providing support that helped us to become professional teachers.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates digital literacy skills among secondary school students at ESP Ruli in Gakenke District, Rwanda, in the context of national efforts to integrate Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into education. Guided by the Constructivist Learning Theory, the research adopts a descriptive survey design and a quantitative approach, complemented by interviews, to assess students' competencies in key digital literacy domains, including basic computer operations, internet navigation, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, online safety, and problem-solving using ICT. The study targets a population of 846 individuals, from which a sample of 109 respondents is selected using both probability and non-probability sampling techniques. Data is collected through questionnaires, interviews, and documentary review, and analyzed using statistical methods such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores. The findings are expected to reveal the current level of students' digital literacy, identify gaps in skills and access to digital tools, and examine the relationship between ICT access and proficiency. Findings 49.4% of students reporting that they always use digital tools and 68.8% of teachers consistently integrating them into their lessons. The findings showed that digital tools enhance students' understanding (69.7%) and increase engagement (82%), while 61.8% of students agreed that ICT tools improve their academic performance. However, the study also identified major challenges, including limited access to computers and the internet (100% of students reported difficulty accessing them), inadequate ICT infrastructure, unreliable electricity (100% dependence), technical problems (97.8%), and insufficient teacher training (12.5%). Additionally, 56.2% of teachers indicated that students tend to use digital platforms more for social media than academic purposes. To address these issues, the study recommends increased government investment in ICT infrastructure, continuous teacher training, improved access to digital resources in schools, and stronger guidance for students on the effective academic use of technology. Overall, addressing these challenges will help maximize the benefits of digital literacy in secondary education.

Keywords: Digital literacy, ICT integration, secondary school students, digital skills, Rwanda education, ESP Ruli, technology in education, student proficiency, digital divide, constructivist learning

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation Acronym	/ Meaning
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ESP RULI	École Secondaire Publique RULI
TPACK	Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound (or in Rwanda: SMART Rwanda Initiative)
ICTC	Information and Communication Technology Competence
n	Sample size
CL	Cooperative learning
UTAB	University of technology and Arts of BYUMBA.
REB	Rwanda Basic Education Board
MINEDUC	Ministry of Education

CHAPTER ONE: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

In the 21st century, digital literacy has become a cornerstone of modern education, essential for personal development, economic advancement, and societal transformation. In Rwanda, a country recognized for its ambitious Vision 2050 and its strategic focus on building a knowledge-based economy, digital literacy among secondary school students is particularly crucial. (Rwanda, 2000; Zhang et al., 2024).

Rwanda Basic Education Board (REB), through the ICT in Education Department, has developed an Operational Manual for ICT in Basic Education in Rwanda (hereinafter referred to as the “Operational Manual”). Its purpose is to guide the integration and effective use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in basic education. The motivation behind this initiative is to promote coordinated use of well-designed technology to disseminate educational resources, connect students and teachers to information, and enhance teacher capacity and student learning across all subject areas.

In this perspective, the Operational Manual outlines REB’s approaches to digital content development, the use of modern instructional technologies, deployment of appropriate hardware, and the implementation of e-learning. The overall aim is to ensure a common understanding of ICT practices and to foster partnership, collaboration, and innovation among government institutions and stakeholders.

The Learning Device Management Guidelines (hereinafter referred to as the “Guidelines”) were developed based on the Operational Manual, which serves as a higher-level document. These Guidelines support Basic Education Schools (pre-primary, primary, secondary schools, including Teacher Training Colleges (TTCs), and special schools). They provide practical guidance on managing digital learning devices and ICT equipment, including network infrastructure, to enhance the integration of ICT in teaching, learning, assessment, and school administration. (Education, 2016).

This policy complements the overall *SMART Rwanda Strategy* and implements the Smart Education Policy (Ministry of ICT & Innovation [MINICT], 2015). The *Education Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP)* outlines three strategic goals to enable education to fulfil its potential in the development of Rwanda: (1) expanding access to education at all levels; (2) improving the quality of education and training; and (3) strengthening the relevance of education and training to the labour market, including the integration of 21st-century skills (Ministry of Education [MINEDUC], 2018).

Technology in education can be used to achieve these goals and address the key challenges of access, quality, equity, relevance and management efficiency with tangible advantages that can be seen and measured in numerous ways.

At primary and secondary levels, gross enrolment ratios are growing, and more children are in school. However, the number of trained teachers to sustain these enrolment ratios is still low. At higher education levels, the levels of enrolment are still very low. Here, technology to support Open and Distance Learning (ODEL) can play a critical role in training new teachers, up-skilling existing unqualified teachers and increasing access to tertiary education. While more children are enrolled in basic education, the key challenge remains the quality of education they are getting. Here, technology can be used to improve the quality of teaching and learning materials through the use of digital learning resources. Multimedia interactive digital content can be used to motivate students, improve conceptual understanding and retention of key topics. ICTs can help simplify the use of regular assessments to keep track of student performance. ICTs can help with real-time data gathering of enrolment, assessments, and performance to improve decision-making and effective management of the education sector, leading to informed prioritization and allocation of resources.

ICTs can also be used to strengthen teacher professional development, thereby contributing to the improvement of the quality of education.

Lastly, students must be prepared for the 21st century and given the abilities needed to succeed and thrive in today's complex, technology-based global economy, and to be active 21st-century global citizens. Some of these skills include Critical Thinking, Problem Solving, Communication, Collaboration and Visualization. Technology in education enables the development of these important skills.

Since 2008, MINEDUC has implemented the One Laptop per Child (OLPC) program at primary schools and computer labs for secondary schools. 250,000 OLPC devices were deployed in 764 schools, thus reaching only 10% of primary students. The program faced challenges in capacity building of teachers due to a high learning curve, the cost of deployment was also high, while it only reached a few students, and lastly, the lack of integration of the program in the normal learning and teaching activities was the main challenge.

For Computer labs, only 5% of secondary schools benefited from the program and the labs were used only for ICT lessons. This policy has now been revised to a “One Digital Identity Per Child” and ‘Smart Classrooms’ in all primary and secondary schools. While a device for every child remains the end goal, MINEDUC is shifting from One Laptop Per Child (OLPC) to the concept of a “Smart Classroom” following changing technology, to reduce costs and increase access and equity.

More importantly, the policy will ensure that technology is integrated in all education processes, i.e. preparation, delivery of lessons, assessments and research. (Education, 2018) The self-regulated term is used to describe the learning performed by anyone who controls and evaluates their own learning guided by strategic actions (planning, monitoring, and personnel evaluation) and by the motivation to learn (Zimmerman, 1990). Thus, this study will describe exploring digital literacy skills among secondary school students, particularly ESP RULI.

1.2. Problem Statement

Despite Rwanda's significant efforts to promote digital literacy through national policies and programs, secondary school students, particularly those in rural schools like ESP Ruli, continue to face challenges in acquiring essential digital skills. Limited access to ICT infrastructure, such as computers, reliable internet, and stable electricity, hinders effective digital learning in this remote setting. Teachers often lack adequate training in integrating technology into their teaching, further exacerbating the problem. Socio-economic disparities prevent many students from accessing digital tools at home, widening the digital divide. Additionally, language barriers and a lack of locally relevant digital content make it difficult for students to engage meaningfully with technology. These challenges collectively impede the goal of equipping students in ESP Ruli with the digital competencies necessary for academic success, future employment, and active participation in a rapidly digitizing world. Addressing these issues requires targeted interventions to ensure equitable access to digital literacy opportunities (Education, 2016).

1.3.1. General Objective

This research aims to evaluate the digital literacy skills of secondary school students and identify areas for targeted improvement.

1.3.2. Specific Objectives

i. To assess the current level of digital literacy skills among ESP RULI students.

those digital literacy skills are :

ii. To identify specific areas where students exhibit strengths and weaknesses in using digital tools and resources in ESP RULI.

iii. To provide actionable recommendations for enhancing digital literacy education in ESP RULI.

1.3.3. Research Questions

1. What is the current level of digital literacy of secondary school students?

2. Which digital tools and resources are most commonly used by these students, and how proficient are they in using them?

3. What gaps exist in students' digital literacy skills, and how can they be addressed?

1.3.4. Research Hypotheses

1. Hypothesis 1

2. H₀₁: Secondary school students do not possess adequate digital literacy skills as mentioned from objective one..

3. H₁₁: Secondary school students possess measurable digital literacy skills.

2. Hypothesis 2

1. H₀₂: There is no relationship between access to digital tools and students' digital proficiency.

2. H₁₂: Access to digital tools significantly influences students' digital proficiency.

3. Hypothesis 3

1. H₀₃: No significant gaps exist in students' digital literacy skills.

2. H₁₃: Significant gaps exist in students' digital literacy skills.

1.3.5. Scope of the Research

1.3.6. Content Scope

The study focuses on digital literacy skills including information access, communication, digital content creation, problem-solving, and online safety.

1.3.7. Geographical Scope

The study was conducted in selected secondary schools (e.g., ESP RULI School or other chosen schools).

1.3.8. Time Scope

The study covers the academic period of the research year.

1.4. Significance of the study

This research is of great importance, first to the researchers, to the government of Rwanda, to UTAB, and to ESP RULI.

- To the Researchers, this study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on digital literacy and provide a solid foundation for further research. It will also help researchers understand the practical challenges faced by students and schools in enhancing digital literacy.
- To the Government of Rwanda, the findings of this study will offer valuable insights for policymakers in developing strategies and policies aimed at bridging the digital divide. By addressing gaps identified in this research, the government can prioritize resources and initiatives to equip students with essential digital skills, fostering national development in a technology-driven world.
- To UTAB, the University of Technology and Arts of Byumba (UTAB) can leverage the study's findings to enhance its own educational programs. The insights can guide the integration of digital literacy training into the curriculum, benefiting current and future students and aligning with UTAB's mission to provide quality education.
- To ESP RULI, these institutions can use the research outcomes to identify and address specific gaps in digital literacy training among their students. By tailoring their programs to the identified needs, they can improve the employability and productivity of their graduates, contributing to the development of the local community and beyond.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Constructivist Learning Theory explains that learners actively construct knowledge through interaction with their environment and experiences. According to Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky, learning occurs when students engage in activities that allow them to explore, collaborate, and solve problems.

In the context of digital literacy, constructivism suggests that students develop digital skills when they interact with digital technologies such as computers, mobile devices, educational software, and the internet. Through activities like searching for information online, creating digital content, and communicating through digital platforms, learners build their understanding and enhance their technological competencies.

This theory therefore supports the idea that secondary school students improve their digital literacy skills when they are given opportunities to actively use digital tools during learning activities (Piaget, 1970; Vygotsky, 1978).

2.2 Historical Background

In the 21st century, digital literacy has become a critical component of education systems worldwide. Students are expected not only to operate digital devices but also to critically evaluate digital information, collaborate online, and create digital content.

Many countries have implemented policies to promote digital literacy among students. In Rwanda, initiatives such as the SMART Rwanda Master Plan aim to integrate ICT into education and develop students' digital competencies necessary for participation in the digital economy (Republic of Rwanda, 2015).

Therefore, understanding the historical development of digital literacy helps explain its growing importance in education and highlights the need for schools to equip students with the digital skills required for modern learning and future employment.

2.3. Definition of Key Concepts

2.3.1. Exploring

Refers to the process of investigating or examining a subject in depth to gain knowledge and understanding. In the context of this study, exploring involves analyzing the digital literacy skills of students to uncover patterns, strengths, and areas for improvement.

2.3.2. Digital

Relates to technologies, devices, or systems that use digital signals for processing, storing, and transmitting information. It encompasses a broad range of tools, including computers, smartphones, and online platforms, which are integral to modern communication and information management.

2.3.3. Literacy

Refers to the ability to read and write. However, in a broader context, it encompasses the knowledge and skills required to interpret and utilize various forms of information effectively. In this study, literacy extends to digital competencies necessary for navigating the digital world.

2.3.4 Skills

These are the abilities and expertise acquired through practice and education. In this study, skills refer specifically to competencies in using digital tools and resources, including technical proficiency, problem-solving, and adaptability in digital contexts.

2.3.5. Digital Skills

An advanced level of digital proficiency that allows an individual to perform specialised and complex functions in Information and Communication Technology and related fields.

2.3. 6. Digital Literacy

According to (Eshet-Alkalai, 2004) emphasizes technological proficiency as the foundational element of digital literacy. He defines digital literacy as the ability to effectively and critically use technology for communication, information gathering, and problem-solving. He proposes a framework that includes several types of literacy, such as:

Photographic literacy (interpreting digital images),

Operational literacy (basic technological skills),

Information literacy (searching and evaluating digital content),

Critical literacy (evaluating the credibility of digital sources),

Creative literacy (using digital tools to create and innovate)

According to (Martin, 2006), digital literacy is "the ability to effectively and critically navigate, evaluate, and create information using a range of digital technologies. In his view:

Digital literacy requires a combination of skills for using digital technologies to create, evaluate, and communicate information.

Martin highlights that digital literacy goes beyond technical skills to include critical engagement with digital content. He stresses the need for information evaluation skills and problem-solving capabilities in the digital environment.

He also emphasizes creativity and innovation, arguing that digital literacy enables students to participate in digital content creation rather than just consumption.

2.3.7. Technological Proficiency

According to (Eshet-Alkalai, 2004), technological proficiency forms the foundation of digital literacy. It involves the ability to operate digital devices, navigate the internet, and use software effectively. However, (Meyers et al., 2013), suggest that while these skills are essential, they represent only one part of a broader digital literacy framework.

2.3.8. Information Literacy

(Leu et al., 2013) argue that information literacy is a critical component of digital literacy, referring to the ability to locate, evaluate, and apply information from digital sources. They emphasize that students need to develop skills to discern credible information amidst the vast amount of content available online, which is essential for academic success.

2.3.9. Communication and Collaboration

(Hobbs, 2010) highlights that communication and collaboration are integral to digital literacy. With the rise of online platforms, students must not only be proficient in using digital communication tools but also understand the nuances of digital citizenship, including ethical behavior, respect for privacy, and the ability to collaborate effectively in virtual environments.

2.3.10. Critical Thinking and Digital Ethics

(Martin, 2006) stresses the importance of critical thinking in the digital age. Digital literacy should empower students to question the content they encounter online, recognize biases, and think critically about the implications of their online actions. Furthermore, (Livingstone & Helsper, 2007) discuss the ethical dimension of digital literacy, particularly the importance of teaching students to navigate issues like digital privacy, security, and online safety.

2.3.11. Creativity and Innovation

(Beetham & Sharpe, 2013) argue that digital literacy also involves the ability to produce digital content and engage in creative practices. For secondary school students, this

includes creating blogs, videos, and using technology to generate innovative solutions to problems.

2.4. The Impact of Digital Literacy on Students' Academic Performance

One interesting finding from the survey was that a majority of students reported using computers at least 4-5 times a week for academic purposes. This showcases the significant role Digital plays in the learning experience of students today. Another noteworthy result was that most students believed that using digital literacy tools positively impacted their academic performance. They expressed those digital tools like computers enhanced their research capabilities, improved their writing skills, and promoted collaboration with classmates.

Interestingly, some students also mentioned a few drawbacks of Digital tools usage, such as distractions from social media and increased screen time. Educators and institutions need to address these concerns and find a balance between the benefits and potential drawbacks of computer-based learning. As for the availability of digital tools, the survey revealed that a vast majority of students had access to personal digital tools at home and computer facilities at their educational institutions. This accessibility further emphasizes the prevalence of digital tools usage in the academic landscape.

Overall, the survey results shed light on the positive effects of digital tools on students' academic performance. However, it's crucial to acknowledge that each student's experience may vary, and it's important to consider individual needs when integrating technology into education.

2.4 Critical Analysis

Digital literacy is increasingly recognized as an essential skill for secondary school students, enabling them to access, evaluate, and create digital content effectively. Globally, students often demonstrate basic functional skills, such as using social media or word processors, but lack critical digital competencies (Gilster, 1997; Martin, 2006). Research shows that teacher competence, curriculum integration, and school learning environments significantly influence students' digital literacy outcomes (Mishra & Koehler, 2006; UNESCO, 2018). In many African countries, including Rwanda, infrastructural challenges such as limited access to computers and internet connectivity constrain students' ability to develop advanced digital skills (Wainaina, 2018). Government initiatives like Rwanda's SMART Education policies aim to address these challenges by integrating ICT into

schools and enhancing both student and teacher competencies (Republic of Rwanda, 2015). At the secondary school level, students' attitudes and motivation further affect engagement with technology, while digital literacy is often treated as an add-on rather than a cross-cutting skill. These gaps underscore the need for context-specific research, particularly at schools like ESP RULI, to identify strategies that effectively develop students' digital literacy. Addressing infrastructure, teacher training, curriculum integration, and student engagement holistically is critical for fostering meaningful digital skills among learners.

2.5 Relationship to the Current Study

The current study builds on existing theories and research on digital literacy. Constructivist theory highlights that students develop skills through active engagement with technology (Piaget, 1970; Vygotsky, 1978), while Digital Literacy Theory defines the competencies needed to navigate digital environments effectively (Gilster, 1997). The TPACK framework emphasizes the role of teachers and curriculum integration in shaping students' digital skills (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Global and African studies indicate that access to devices, internet connectivity, teacher support, and student motivation influence digital literacy outcomes (Martin, 2006; UNESCO, 2018; Wainaina, 2018). In Rwanda, initiatives like the SMART Rwanda Master Plan aim to enhance ICT integration in schools (Republic of Rwanda, 2015). This study examines how these factors affect secondary school students at ESP RULI, addressing context-specific gaps in understanding digital literacy development.

2.6 Research Gap Analysis

Although digital literacy has been widely studied globally, there is limited research focused on secondary school students in Rwanda, particularly at schools like ESP RULI (Wainaina, 2018; Martin, 2006). Existing studies rarely examine how teacher ICT competence, curriculum integration, access to devices, and students' attitudes collectively influence digital literacy outcomes (Mishra & Koehler, 2006; UNESCO, 2018; Republic of Rwanda, 2015). Moreover, most research focuses on isolated aspects of digital skills rather than assessing multiple dimensions simultaneously. This study addresses these gaps by providing a comprehensive evaluation of students' digital literacy levels and the contextual factors affecting skill development in Rwandan secondary schools.

2.5. Conceptual framework

A conceptual framework shows the relationship between the independent and the dependent variables. The interaction of the variables' relationship is indicated by the arrows. In this study, the conceptual framework was based on the relationship between the use of Digital literacy and the teaching and learning process. The use of Digital literacy is the independent variable, while the teaching and learning process is the dependent variable, as shown in the figure below:

Variable Type	Variable	Description
Independent Variable	Digital literacy factors	ICT resources, internet access, training, and infrastructure
Intervening Variable	School & student support conditions	Teaching methods, attitudes, management support, guidance
Dependent Variable	Digital literacy skills	Students' ability to use digital tools effectively

Table 1: Independent and Dependent Variables

Figure 1: Conceptual framework use in learning

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study will adopt a **descriptive survey research design**. This design is appropriate because it allows the researcher to collect information from secondary school students regarding their digital literacy skills, digital tools usage, and proficiency levels.

The descriptive design enables systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of data to describe the current status of digital literacy among students.

3.2 Research Approach

The study will use a **quantitative research approach**.

This approach is suitable because:

- It allows the collection of numerical data.
- It enables statistical analysis of students' digital literacy levels.
- It helps test research hypotheses objectively.
- Mixed Methods (interview).

3.3 Study Population

The target population will consist of:

- Secondary school students
- Teachers (optional)
- School administrators (optional)

3.3.1. Target populations

A population is a collection of objects, events, or individuals having some common characteristics that researchers are interested in studying. Population can be defined as a group of categories of human beings, animals, and other things that have one or more traits in common (Mouton, 1996). Our research population is located at ESP RULI in RULI Sector, GAKENKE District. The target population for this research is composed of three categories of people, including school leaders, students, and teachers. The whole population is 846

Table 2: Research Population

Categories	Number
Students	823
Teachers	19
Administrative leaders	4
Total	846

Source: Primary data 2025- 2026

3.4. Sampling

3.4.1 Probability sampling

Probability sampling is a sampling method that involves randomly selecting a sample, or a part of the population that you want to research. It is also sometimes called random sampling. This method is used whereby all students studying at ESP are involved.

3.4.2 Non-probability Sampling

Non-probability sampling is a sampling technique where the odds of any member being selected for a sample cannot be calculated. The purposive sampling method is used to select staff members and teachers since they possess relevant information about attitudes on the use of smart classrooms in teaching and learning processes in secondary schools in different subjects.

3.4.3. Sample size

A sample is a part of the population, which is deliberately selected for investigation of the sample size from the targeted population (Williams, 1997).

To facilitate the work, we select a sample of 89 students to represent others by the use of the Simple Random Sampling.

formula: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)}$ where $e=0.1$

Therefore, $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)} = \frac{823}{1+823(0.1)^2} = 89.2 \approx 89$, where n is the sample size, N is the total population, and e is the significance level. The sample size of our study is composed of 89 students from 823 students, as it is given by Yamane’s formula. We also used 16

teachers from 19 teachers and 4 school leaders, who were also obtained by using Yamane’s formula. The total sample size is made up of 109 individuals.

At ESP RULI, the total number of teachers was **19**. Using a 5% margin of error, the

sample size was calculated as follows: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)} = \frac{19}{1+19(0.05)^2} = 18.4$

The calculated sample size was approximately **18 teachers**. However, due to availability and accessibility of respondents during data collection, **16 teachers** participated in the study.

Table 3: Sample size

Categories	Sampling Method	Sample size
Students	Simple Random Sampling	89
Teachers	Purposive Sampling	16
School leaders	Population / Census	4
Total	Mixed Sampling Approach	109

Source: primary data, 2025-2026

3.5 Data Collection Procedure

The researcher will follow these steps:

Obtain permission from school authorities.

Explain study purpose to respondents.

Distribute questionnaires to selected participants.

Collect completed questionnaires.

Conduct interviews and observations where necessary.

3.6. Data Collection Instruments

The data collection instruments that were used in this study are: documentary, interview, and questionnaire techniques.

3.6.1. Documentary technique

Mutaganda (2008:41), this tool is used in the collection of data that already exists in boxes in some organizations, documents, computers, and libraries. It is used purposely in analyzing the historical background, newspapers, reports, and the internet. The documentary technique is used to go through different theoretical and conceptual views about the comparative study of learners’ performance in the computer science subject.

3.6.2. Questionnaire

The questionnaire technique is defined as a set of questions that are asked to get information from a respondent. A questionnaire is a carefully designed instrument (written) for collecting data directly from people (Audrey, 1979). This is the most generally used tool, especially in quantitative and qualitative research. Open-ended questions were designed to allow respondents to give detailed information concerning their intentions, attitudes, and opinions on the research problem. Closed-ended questions, on the other hand, were designed to clarify response alternatives and reduce the number of unclear responses that could be given by the respondents. The researchers gave the questionnaire to teachers and students of ESP RULI in Gakenke district.

3.6.3. Interview

(Garawitz, 1999), an interview is a procedure of scientific investigation using a verbal communication process in order to collect information related to the set objectives, which constitute the finality of the research hypothesis. The interview technique consists of organizing a conversation in which the investigator asks questions to the surveyed person to gather information on the hypothesis and the concept indicators

3.7. Data Collection Procedure

The researcher will follow these steps:

1. Obtain permission from school authorities.
2. Explain study purpose to respondents.
3. Distribute questionnaires to selected participants.
4. Collect completed questionnaires.
5. Conduct interviews and observations where necessary.

3.8. Ethical Considerations

The study will observe research ethics by:

- Obtaining informed consent from participants
- Ensuring confidentiality of responses
- Using data strictly for academic purposes

Allowing voluntary participation

3.9 Data Analysis Procedures

Collected data will be analyzed using statistical methods such as:

- Frequencies
- Percentages
- Tables and charts
- Mean scores
- Statistical analysis will be conducted using software such as **SPSS**.

Results will be presented using tables and graphs for interpretation.

3.10. Reliability and Validity of Research

Reliability ensures consistency of results.

A **pilot study** will be conducted in a school not included in the main study. Reliability will be tested using internal consistency methods such as **Cronbach's Alpha**.

The questionnaire will be reviewed by:

- Research supervisor
- Education experts
- ICT specialists

Corrections and recommendations will be incorporated before data collection.

No	ITEMS	COST
1	Printing	20,000RWF
2	Binding	10,000RWF
3	Photocopying	4,000RWF
4	Communication & internet	40,000RWF
5	Transport	50,000RWF
6	Meals	80,000RWF
	Total	204.000RWF

3.7.4 Budget and timeline

Budget

Therefore, to accomplish this dissertation, the researchers will use the following budget

Table 4: Budget

Timeline

Dates for Activities	Activity to be done
1 st November to 10 th November 2025	Formulation of the topic
16 th November to 26 th December, 2025	Re-submitting the amended proposal to the supervisor
01 st January 2026	Submitting a research proposal
05 th January to 15 th January 2026	Data collection
18 th January to 18 th March 2026	Submission of the research project and presentation

Table 5: Time

Table 5 highlighting the timeline and plan of work of the activities and items required to implement the proposed research.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1. Presentation of information from students

4.1.1. Profile of the students

In this part of the study, the researchers identify the students according to their gender, age, and level of education.

Table 6: Students' profile

Students' characteristics		Frequency	%
Gender	Male	39	43.8
	Female	50	56.2
Total		89	100
Age	Below 13	12	13.5
	13-15	28	31.5
	16-19	34	38.2
	20 and over 20	15	16.9
Total		89	100
Education Level	O' level	48	53.9
	A-level	41	46.1
Total		89	100

Source: primary data

Table 6 above shows that among 89 respondents 39 that equal to 43.8 %, are male, while 50 that equal to 56.2%, are female. Also, it shows that 13.5% students are below 13 ages, 31,5% have between 13-15 age, 38.2% have between 16-19 age, other 16.9% students' have 20 and over 20 ages. However, it shows that 53.9% are in ordinary level while 46.1% are in advanced level.

4.1.2 The extent of Digital tools uses in learning at ESP Ruli

Table 7: Digital tools technologies in the class

Questions	Answer	Frequency	%
How often do you encounter Digital tools technologies in your classes?	Rarely	0	0
	Occasionally	13	14.6
	Frequently	33	37.1
	Always	44	49.4
Total		89	100

Source: Primary source

Information summarized in this table7 shows that students encounter Digital tools technologies in their classes, where 49.4% of the total respondents said that they encounter Digital tools technologies always, 37.7% students reported that they encounter them frequently, whereas 14.6% students replied that they encounter it occasionally.

4.1.3 Factors that influence students' attitudes to use Digital tools like computer at ESP Ruli

Table 8: Factors that influence students' attitude to use Digital tools

Statements	A		N		D	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
1. Teachers in our school provide homework as it is the best opportunity to search on the internet	26	29	2	2.2	61	68.5
2. If I find difficult concepts, I visit the internet for more understanding	36	40.5	21	23.5	32	27.9
3. Using ICT tools for learning would improve my learning and academic performance	55	61.8	0	0	34	38.2
4. I can complete tasks or a search if there was no one around to tell me what to do	42	47.2	8	8.98	39	43.8
5.It is easy for me to get access to the Computer with internet when I need to search	0	0	0	0	89	100

Source: primary data,2025-2026

The first statement from table 8 ,asked about how teachers provide the homework in the best manner to be done by using the internet, 29% of respondents agreed that teachers provide them the homework in the best manner to be done by using the internet, and 2(2.2%) were neutral to the statement. Also, the findings revealed that the majority, 36(40.5%) of the students consult the internet for more understanding when they find difficult concepts, 27.9% said that they can't consult the internet when they find difficult concepts, while 23.5% were neutral. The results also showed how the students 'attitudes about the use of ICT tools to improve their Digital Literacy and their academic learning. The response from the student respondents revealed that 61.8%of respondents accepted that the use of ICT improves their Digital Literacy and their academic performance, while 38.2% of students disagreed with the statements, and 3 of them did not want to discuss how the use of ICT improves their learning and affects their academic performance. Other points of views were how the students complete their task by using internet when there is no one around to help them most of them 47.2% accepted that they can complete tasks or a search if there was no one around to tell them what to do and 43.8% disagreed that they can't complete tasks or a search if there was no one around to tell them what to do and the rest 8.98% were not understand the questions and refused to show their views about statements however, all respondents that is equal 89(100%) they replied that isn't easy for them to get access to internet when they need to search.

4.1.4. Advantages do Digital tools offer for your learning?

Questions		Frequency	%
In your opinion, what advantages do Digital tools offer for your learning?	Increased engagement	16	17.9
	Improved understanding	62	69.7
	Enhanced collaboration	11	12.4
	Other (please specify)	0	0
TOTAL		89	100

Table 9: The advantages do Digital tools offer for your learning

Source: primary data,2025_2026

Figure 2: The advantages do Digital tools offer for your learning

Table 9 above shows that 69% of students said that the use of Digital tools in their learning improved understanding, 17.9% of students replied that it increased understanding, while 12.4% of the total respondents revealed that it enhanced collaboration.

4.1.5 Challenges of using Digital tools in the learning process at ESP Ruli

Table 10: Challenges of using Digital tools in the learning process

S/N	Items	Agree(A)		Disagree (D)	
		F	%	F	%
1	Numerous Digital devices, including laptops, tablets, projectors, software, etc., are required for improving digital literacy.	89	100	0	0
2	When technology advances, software and hardware requirements also often.	87	97.8	2	2.2
3	There are not enough qualified teachers.	89	100	0	0
4	Technical issues are common with Digital devices	87	97.8	2	2.2
5	Electronic equipment frequently has technical problems.	86	96.6	3	3.4
6	High maintenance cost	89	100	0	0
7	Highly dependent on electricity	89	100	0	0

Source: Primary data, 2025-2026. Where A: Agree, D: Disagree

According to the information summarized in Table 10 above, showed that a Digital Literacy requires a variety of Digital devices, including computers, tablets, projectors, software and technical issues are common with electronic devices; however, they are prone to technical problems and depend heavily on electricity.

4.1.6 Impacts of Digital literacy in learning at ESP Ruli

Table 11: Impacts do Digital literacy offer for your learning

	Answer	F	%
In your opinion, what impacts do Digital literacy offer for your learning?	Enhanced engagement	73	82
	Difficult to read content	5	5.6
	Collaborative learning	11	12.4
	Other (please specify)	0	0
Total		89	100

Source: primary data, 2025-2026

The results from Table 11 students show that Digital literacy technologies enhanced engagement in their learning as perceived by 82% of the total respondents, even if it is difficult to access content, as said by 5.6%, and 12.4% of respondents replied that they enhance collaborative learning, as shown in Table 6 above.

4.2 Presentation of information from teachers

Table 12: Teacher's profile

		Frequency	%
Gender	Male	6	37.5
	Female	10	62.5
Total		16	100
Experience	1-5 years	4	25
	6-10 years	9	56.2

	above 10 years	3	18.8
Total		16	100
Qualification	A2	0	0
	A1	7	43.8
	A0	9	56.2
Total		16	100

Source: primary data, 2025-2026

Table 12 above shows that among 16 teachers, 6, which is equal to 37.5 %, are male, while 10 that equal to 62.5%, are female. Also, it shows that 25% teachers have experience between 1-5years, 56.2% have between 6-10 years, and 18.8% have above 10 years. This table also shows that 43.8% have A1 while 56.2% have A0.

4.2.2 The extent of Digital tools uses in teaching at ESP Ruli

		Frequencies	%
How frequently do you integrate smart classroom technologies into your teaching?	Rarely	0	0
	Occasionally	0	0
	Frequently	5	31.2
	Always	11	68.8
TOTAL		16	100

Table 13: Extent of Digital tools use in teaching

Source: primary source, 2025-2026

Figure 3: Extent of Digital tools use in teaching

From Table 13, Data analysis shows that teachers integrate smart classroom technologies in their teaching, where 11(68.8%) of teachers said that they always integrate smart classroom technologies in their teaching, while 31.2% of teachers reported that they frequently integrate smart classroom technologies in their teaching.

4.2.3 Factors that influence Digital Literacy in Teaching at ESP Ruli

Table 14: Factors that influence Digital Literacy in Teaching

Statements	A		N		D	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
Learning from the Digital tools does not take place only in a smart classroom	13	81.2	0	0	3	18.8
The Digital Literacy increased the interaction between the teacher and students	6	37.5	2	12.5	8	50
Teachers give the opportunity to search the internet library to the students	10	62.5	1	6.3	5	31.2
The most visited websites are those of social media rather than websites for learning	9	56.2	2	12.5	5	31.2
When I find difficult concepts, I visit internet for more understanding	8	50	2	12.5	6	37.5
In 30 periods of a week, I prepare 6 lessons to be delivered in the smart classroom using Digital tools like computers, internet & projector	2	12.5	0	0	14	87.5

Source: primary data, 2025-2026

Figure 4: Factors that influence Digital Literacy in Teaching

As to whether from table 14, learning from the internet does not take place only in a smart classroom, the findings revealed that many respondents (81.2%) proclaimed that they agreed with the statement, and 18.8% disagree with this statement. This means that students can access the internet from anywhere for learning rather than in school. The respondents answered about the interaction between teachers and students, where 50% disagreed with the statement that smart learning increased their interaction between them and their students, 37.5% of teachers accepted that smart learning increased their interaction between them and students, while the 12.5% were neutral. The findings revealed that 56.2% of teachers said that website visited mostly by students, are those of social media than website of searching for learning which means that the social media are highly appreciated in the schools, 31.2% of respondents disagreed with statements saying that website visited the most by students, are those of social media than website of searching for learning while the 12.5% were neutral. The other points revealed in Table 9, the majority of teacher (87.5%) disagree that in 30 periods of a week, they prepare 6 lessons to be delivered in the smart classroom using Digital tools like computers, internet & projector while a few of them that is equal (12.5%) agree that in 30 periods of a week, they prepare 6 lessons to be delivered in the smart classroom using Digital tools like computers internet & projector.

4.2.3 Benefits of Digital literacy bring to the teaching process at ESP Ruli.

Table 15: Benefits of Digital literacy bring to the teaching process

Questions	Answer	Frequencies	%
What benefits do you believe	Increased engagement	2	12.5
Digital literacy brings to the	Improved understanding	7	43.8
teaching process?	Enhanced collaboration	7	43.8
	Other (please specify)	0	0
TOTAL		16	100

Source: Primary data, 2025-2026

The respondents of teachers for benefits from table15, do they believe Digital literacy brings to the teaching process 12.5% teachers said that improve engagement, 43.8% of teachers replied that improve understanding, other 43.8% respondents revealed that increase engagement of students in the lesson.

4.2.4 Challenge faced by teachers and Leaders while utilizing Digital Table 16: Challenge you face in effectively utilizing Digital literacy

Questions	Answer	F	%
What challenge do you face in	Lack of training	2	12.5
effectively utilizing Digital literacy	Technical issues	12	75
technologies?	Resistance from students	2	12.5
	Other (please specify)	0	0
Total		16	100

Source: Primary data, 2025-2026

From table 16, The respondents of teachers for obstacles they face in effectively utilizing Digital literacy technologies, who faced technical issues 74%, Lack of training 12.5 %, Resistance from students 12.5%, Other (please specify) 0%.

4.4.5 Data from interview and from school leader

Table 17: Interview Responses from School Leader

Question	Response Option	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Q1. % of classrooms equipped with smart technologies	More than 75%	1	80%
Total			80%
Q2. How Digital classrooms positively influence education	Enhanced institutional reputation	1	22%
	Improved student outcomes		56%
	Better faculty satisfaction		11%
	Other		11%
Total		1	100%
Q3. Challenges in implementing digital tools	Budget constraints		50%
	Technical support issues		33%
	Resistance from faculty		17%
	Other		0%
Total			100%
Q4. Recommendations to improve smart classroom integration	Increased training opportunities	1	61%
	Enhanced technical support		33%
	Encouragement of innovative teaching methods		22%
	Other		6%
Total		1	100%
Q7. Do smart classrooms increase student engagement?	Yes		78%
	No		11%
Total			100%

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

Overall, the study shows that digital literacy plays a vital role in enhancing secondary education, and the research objectives have been largely met. It is evident that when teachers and students can use digital tools effectively, learning becomes more interactive, engaging, and meaningful. Students gain access to a broader range of resources, while teachers can deliver lessons in innovative ways. Both teachers and students recognize the value of digital literacy and its positive impact on the quality of education.

However, the study also highlights significant challenges that limit its full implementation. Many schools face limited or outdated ICT infrastructure, unreliable internet, inconsistent electricity, and a shortage of quality devices. Teachers often require more training and support to confidently integrate technology into their teaching. These constraints mean that, despite clear benefits, digital literacy is not yet fully realized in practice.

Addressing these challenges is essential for maximizing the impact of digital literacy. Continuous teacher training, investment in reliable ICT infrastructure, provision of quality digital devices, and stable internet and power supply are key. Equally important is fostering a culture that encourages the meaningful use of digital tools in everyday teaching and learning.

These findings align with global recommendations, such as those from UNESCO (2018), emphasizing the importance of strengthening digital education systems to promote educational equity and sustainable development. Digital literacy has the potential to equip students with the skills needed to succeed in a rapidly changing digital world.

5.2. Recommendations

From the research findings, in order to improve the best use of Digital literacy in secondary school students, as their attitude towards the effective and efficient teaching and learning process is positive, the following recommendations may be considered:

5.2.1 To the Government

- The government should provide smart classrooms for all schools.
- It should give better quality equipment in smart classrooms and digital devices (POSITIVO Computers faced different problems like less processing power, crashing, unavailable spare parts, ...)

- It should provide enough and strong infrastructures which support better use of digital literacy, like electricity, internet, ...
- The government should provide high-speed internet in all schools.
- There should be an ICT technician at the regional education levels to help teachers with the computer hardware or the software, and assist the teachers in handling any computer breakdown.

5.2.2 To the Ministry of Education

- The Ministry of Education should give effective formation and training of the teachers for using Digital tools and interacting with artificial intelligence (AI) in the teaching and learning process in secondary schools.
- More trainers should be deployed to the schools to train the students and teachers on the effective use of computers to increase confidence in the teaching and learning process using Digital tools.
- The Ministry of Education should oversee how Digital tools are useful in the teaching and learning process in secondary schools.

5.2.4 To the School Administration

- The school administration should familiarize themselves with the national smart classrooms policies that would enable them integrate the use of Digital literacy in the teaching and learning process.
- Schools should plan for other places to access the computers from, like the library and the staffroom, to help both teachers and learners become familiar with computers.
- The days and hours for accessing digital tools should be increased in the public secondary schools, as well as in private schools.

5.2.4 To the teachers

- Teacher Should Practices every day to Use Digital Tools and try every day to Be Update Because Technology Advance Every Time.
- Teachers must guide the learners while they are using Digital tools in order to protect the equipment and tools.

5.2.6 To other society members

- Society members, like parents and neighbors will help the learners to use ICT tools and to help learners to research by using ICT equipment.
- They should protect or secure smart classroom equipment or facilities like wires, electricity cables, computers....

5.2.7 Recommendations to researchers

- To investigate the attitude towards the use of Digital literacy in the teaching and learning process.
- To investigate the importance of teaching and learning courses using Digital tools.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Introductory letter

Dear respondents,

We are **IRADUKUNDA Gervais and KARANGWA Vainqueur Alain**, students of UTAB in the faculty of education. We are conducting a research about the attitude on the Exploring digital literacy among the secondary school students for the sake of completing the requirements for the Bachelor's degree with honor in Mathematics and Computer Science with Education. We kindly request you to offer us a support and spend your time filling this questionnaire. Please, dear respondents, as indicated your responses are highly valued and confidential and will ensure that the required information for our research is adequate.

Your cooperation is highly appreciated.

Appendix 2: Questionnaire designed for students

I. Instructions

1. Put (v) in the box corresponding to your choice and explain where necessary.
2. For some questions, answer in the space provided.
3. Do not write your name anywhere in this questionnaire.
4. Respond in English.

Section I: Profile of respondents

What is your gender?

Male Female

What is your age?

Age	
Below 13	
12-15	
16-19	
20 and Over 20	

What educational level are you currently in?

O'level A'level

Section II: Questions

Q1. How often do you encounter Digital ltools technologies in your school?

- A. Rarely
- B. Occasionally
- C. Frequently
- D. Always

Appendix 2: Questionnaire designed for students

I. Instructions

1. Put (v) in the box corresponding to your choice and explain where necessary.
2. For some questions, answer in the space provided.
3. Do not write your name anywhere in this questionnaire.
4. Respond in English.

Section I: Profile of respondents

1. What is your gender?

Male Female

2. What is your age?

Age	
Below 13	
12-15	
16-19	
20 and Over 20	

3. What educational level are you currently in?

O'level A'level

Section II: Questions

Q1. How often do you encounter Digital ltools technologies in your school?

- A. Rarely
- B. Occasionally
- C. Frequently
- D. Always

Q2. Please indicate the extent to which you agree (A), Disagree (D), and Neutral (N) on the following statement regarding the factors that influence attitude to use smart classroom

Statements	A	N	D
Teachers in our school provide homework as it is the best opportunity to search on the internet			
If I find difficult concepts, I visit the internet for more understanding			
Using ICT tools for learning would improve my learning and academic performance			
I can complete tasks or a search if there was no one around to tell me what to do			
It is easy for me to get access to the internet and digital tools when I need to search			
Artificial intelligence (AI) has positive impacts in your learning process			

Q3. In your opinion, what advantages do Digital literacy offer for your learning?

- A. Improved access to resources
- B. Enhanced interactivity
- C. Better understanding of topics
- D. Other (please

Q4. Please indicate the extent to which you agree (A), Disagree (D), with a given perception on the challenges of using a smart classroom in the learning process.

S/N	Items	A	D
1	Numerous Digital tools, including laptops, tablets, projectors, software, etc., are required for Digital literacy.		
2	When technology advances, software and hardware requirements also change often.		
3	There are not enough qualified teachers.		
4	Technical issues are common with electronic devices		
5	Electronic equipment frequently has technical problems.		
6	High maintenance cost		
7	Highly dependent on electricity		

Q5. In your opinion, what Impacts do Digital literacy offer for your learning?

- a) Enhanced engagement
- b) Difficult to rich content
- c) Collaborative learning
- d) Other (please specify)

Thank you

Appendix3: Interview questions designed for teachers

Dear teachers,

We are conducting a study about attitudes on the use of smart classrooms in teaching and learning processes in secondary schools, and would like to invite you to participate in the study. Your careful thought can be important for improving the pedagogical method used in the teaching process. Please complete the questionnaire by ticking off the appropriate box that best represents your view. Certainly, your responses will be strictly confidential and used only for research purposes

Section I: Profile of respondents

1. What is your gender?

- a. Male
- b. Female

2. What is your qualification?

- a. Secondary diploma (A₂)
- b. Advanced diploma (A₁)
- c. Bachelor's degree (A₀)

3. What is your experience in a teaching career?

- a. 1-5 years
- b. 6-10 years
- c. above 10 years

Q1. How frequently do you integrate Digital technologies into your teaching?

- A. Rarely
- B. Occasionally
- C. Frequently
- D. Always

Q2. Please indicate the extent to which you agree (A), Disagree (D), and Neutral (N) on the following statement regarding the factors that influence attitude to use smart classroom

Statements	A	N	D
Learning from the internet does not take place only in a smart classroom			
The smart classroom increased the interaction between the teacher and students			
Teachers give the opportunity to search the internet library to the			

students			
The most visited websites are those of social media rather than website of searching for learning			
When I find difficult concepts, I visit the internet for more understanding			
In 30 periods of a week, I prepare 6 lessons to be delivered in the smart classroom using the internet & projector			

Q3. What benefits do you believe smart classrooms bring to the teaching process?

- A. Increased engagement
- B. Improved understanding
- C. Enhanced collaboration
- D. Other (please specify)

Q4. What challenges do you face in effectively utilizing Digital technologies?

- A. Lack of training
- B. Technical issues
- C. Resistance from students
- D. Other (please specify)

Q5. What impacts do smart classrooms offer for your teaching?

- a. Efficient classroom management
- b. Real-time assessment
- c. Personalised learning
- d. Other (please specify)

Thank you for your participation.

Appendix 4: Interview questions designed for school administration

Q1. What percentage of classrooms in the institution are equipped with smart technologies?

- A. Less than 25%
- B. 25% - 50%
- C. 50% - 75%
- D. More than 75%

Q2. From your perspective, how have Digital classrooms positively influenced the overall educational environment?

- A. Enhanced institutional reputation
- B. Improved student outcomes
- C. Better faculty satisfaction
- D. Other (please specify)

Q3. What challenges have been identified in the implementation and maintenance of Digital tools?

- A. Budget constraints
- B. Technical support issues
- C. Resistance from faculty
- D. Other (please specify)

Q4. What recommendations do you have for improving the integration of smart classrooms in teaching and learning?

- A. Increased training opportunities
- B. Enhanced technical support
- C. Encouragement of innovative teaching methods
- D. Other (please specify)

Q5. From your perspective as administrator, what are the key advantages of Digital literacy?

Q6. In your experience, how does the use of smart technology positively impact the Digital literacy in teaching and learning process?

.....

Q7 From your point of view, do smart classrooms contribute to increased student engagement? Why or why not?

Thank you for your participation.

Appendix 5: Pictures of the school and sample of answered questions

Figure 5: Photo of the school 1

Figure 6: Photo of the school 2

I. Instructions

- 1. Put (v) in the box corresponding to your choice and explain where necessary.
- 2. For some questions, answer in the space provided.
- 3. Do not write your name anywhere in this questionnaire.
- 4. Respond in English.

Section I: Profile of respondents

1. What is your gender?

Male Female

2. What is your age?

Age	
Below 13	
12-15	
16-19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
20 and Over 20	

3. What educational level are you currently in?

O'level A'level

Section II: Questions

Q1. How often do you encounter Digital ltools technologies in your school?

- A. Rarely
- B. Occasionally
- C. Frequently
- D. Always

<input type="checkbox"/>
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>

Q2. Please indicate the extent to which you agree (A), Disagree (D), and Neutral (N) on the following statement regarding the factors that influence attitude to use smart classroom

Statements	A	N	D
Teachers in our school provide homework as it is the best opportunity to search on the internet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
If I find difficult concepts, I visit the internet for more understanding	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
Using ICT tools for learning would improve my learning and academic performance	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
I can complete tasks or a search if there was no one around to tell me what to do		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Q3. In your opinion, what advantages do Digital literacy offer for your learning?

- A. Improved access to resources
- B. Enhanced interactivity
- C. Better understanding of topics
- D. Other (please

Q4. Please indicate the extent to which you agree (A), Disagree (D), with a given perception on the challenges of using a smart classroom in the learning process.

S/N	Items	A	D
1	Numerous Digital tools, including laptops, tablets, projectors, software, etc., are required for Digital literacy.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	When technology advances, software and hardware requirements also change often.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	There are not enough qualified teachers.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4	Technical issues are common with electronic devices	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Electronic equipment frequently has technical problems.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	High maintenance cost	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Highly dependent on electricity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q5. In your opinion, what Impacts do Digital literacy offer for your learning?

- a) Enhanced engagement
- b) Difficult to rich content
- c) Collaborative learning
- d) Other (please specify)

Thank you.

Figure 7: Sample of answered questions

Appendix 6. Introduction Letter For Data Collection

UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY AND ARTS OF BYUMBA
OFFICE OF THE FACULTY OF EDUCATION

Post. Box: 25, Byumba, Gicumbi District
Northern Province, Republic of Rwanda
Phone: +250 - 789 350 053
Email: info@utab.ac.rw
Web: www.utab.ac.rw

INTRODUCTION LETTER FOR DATA COLLECTION

Date: 20/01/2026

To Whom it may concern,

RE: Research Authorization

This is to confirm that IRADUKUNDA Gervais..... whose registration number: UG 113492 And KAREN GWA YAMBURO Hain whose registration number: UG 113845 are bona fide students at the University of Technology and Arts of Byumba (UTAB), pursuing a Bachelor's Degree of Education in MATHEMATICS..... and COMPUTER SCIENCE.....

The student(s) are currently conducting research as part of their academic requirements. The title of the research is:

“Expanding digital literacy skills among secondary school students”

Case study: ES P Ruli

We kindly request your support in providing relevant information that will assist in completing this research. Please note that all collected data will be used strictly for academic purposes and will be handled with confidentiality.

Any assistance you provide to the student in conducting this study will be highly appreciated.

Thank you for your cooperation.

Sincerely,

Dr. Emmanuel NTAKIRUTIMANA
Dean of Faculty of Education

Educatio - Scientia - Minteria

Figure 8: Introduction Letter For Data Collection